

CLINICAL AND OPHTHALMOLOGICAL FEATURES OF CONGENITAL CATARACT IN CHILDREN WITH HIGH DEGREE MYOPIA

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Abstract. *The given article is devoted to the study of clinical and ophthalmological features of children with congenital cataracts against the background of high myopia. The study included 24 (40 eyes) children with cataracts and high myopia, aged from 1 year to 12 years. All patients underwent surgical treatment after ophthalmological examination. The results of the study showed that zonular and posterior capsular forms of cataracts are most often observed in children with congenital cataracts against the background of high myopia. The existing destruction, liquefaction and detachment of the vitreous body requires minimally invasive surgical intervention using modern technologies in ophthalmic surgery.*

Keywords: *congenital cataract, high myopia, vitreous body.*

Introduction. It is important to suggest that congenital cataracts are a fairly common eye pathology in children, accounting for 60% of all congenital defects of the visual organ and is one of the main causes of congenital blindness and low vision (10.0-19.5%) [1,2,6,9].

At present time it is proven that mutation of certain genes leads to the development of cataracts. Congenital changes in the lens can be both isolated and combined with damage to other organs and systems or with eye anomalies, as well as other anomalies, congenital cataracts can develop as a result of intrauterine pathology due to the influence of teratogenic factors on the fetus. Opacities of the lens can be a consequence of a number of intrauterine viral infections - rubella, cytomegalovirus, chickenpox, herpes, influenza [3,4,5,8]. In this case, the mother may have no symptoms or only mild symptoms. As a result, the disease goes unnoticed by the woman, but leads to the development of anomalies in the fetus, including cataracts [2,10,11,12]. Congenital myopia, detected in children during the first three years of life, is usually characterized by a high degree (55-91% of cases), an increase in the length of the anterior-posterior axis (APA), anisometropia (45-55%), astigmatism (40%), a decrease in corrected visual acuity (over 90%), changes in the fundus associated with developmental anomalies of the optic nerve (atypical shape, oblique entry into the sclera, the "bindweed" symptom, pseudo-stagnant papilla, coloboma, atypical cones) and the macular region (hyperpigmentation, hypoplasia, "parquet" or, conversely, albinotic fundus).

It is known that frequently (in 19.4%, according to R.S. Sorokina et al.), congenital myopia is combined with various types of pathology and anomalies in the development of the eye, such as nystagmus, strabismus, colobomas of the eye membranes, subluxation of the lens, partial or complete cataract, Sphero phakia, lenticonus, remnants of embryonic tissue, pathology of the pigment epithelium, partial atrophy of the optic nerve, as well as with various systemic ectodermal malformations and various types of connective tissue dysplasia (Marfan, Stickler, Marchesani; blue sclera, chest deformity, flat feet, umbilical hernias, arachnodactyly, etc.) [13,14,15,16]. The introduction of ultrasound phacoemulsification and standard implantation of posterior chamber IOLs into the capsular bag into everyday clinical practice has significantly reduced the percentage

of secondary cataracts and vitreoretinal complications in patients with cataracts and high myopia. This is due to the blocking of the lens zone sprouts by the haptic elements of the IOL and, in addition, the important role of the IOL optics, which prevents the spread of the proliferative process into the central optical region of the posterior capsule. According to many ophthalmic surgeons, the percentage of occurrence of posterior lens capsule opacities can be reduced by implanting such a model of posterior chamber IOL, which, due to complete straightening and tension of the capsular bag of the removed lens, can create a tight contact between it and the IOL, blocking the migration of lens epithelial cells from the equatorial zone to the central region of the posterior capsule, which prevents the development of secondary cataracts, and also prevents the displacement of the vitreous body. Most posterior chamber IOLs have an angle of inclination of the haptic elements in relation to the IOL optics from 5 to 10 degrees. Therefore, between the optical part of the intraocular lens and the posterior capsule of the removed lens, there is always a gap through which the lens of epithelial cells can spread.

It should be admitted that according to a number of authors, with high myopia, cataracts occur ten times more often than in the population. High myopia is one of the risk factors for cataract surgery, such as damage to the posterior lens capsule and the development of retinal detachment in the postoperative period [10,17,19]. Myopia is characterized by the development of a nuclear form of cataract with a nuclear density of 3-4, which significantly increases the energy and hydrodynamic load on the intraocular tissues, and this increases the risk of developing keratopathy in the postoperative period [1,8,18,20].

Modern technology of cataract phacoemulsification through small incisions, provided that the anterior capsulorhexis is performed qualitatively, "softer" hydrodynamic parameters are used, delicate manipulations are performed, and gentle ultrasound modulation modes are used, allowing for the removal of the lens in cases of high myopia without the risk of vitreoretinal complications. The phacoemulsification method occupies a leading position in modern cataract surgery. The relative closure of the eye cavity during manipulations, a small self-sealing incision, and the possibility of reliable intracapsular fixation of the IOL reduce the likelihood of severe intra- and postoperative complications, which contributes to rapid visual and social rehabilitation of patients. In the course of literature analysis, we identified the causes leading to refractive errors in the calculation of the IOL in cataract surgery on eyes after keratorefractive operations. First of all, this is the incorrectness of determining the refractive power of the cornea with standard keratometers and keratotopographs based on disks.

According to most researchers, during standard keratometry, there is a significant overestimation of the refractive power of the cornea, which leads to a shift in refraction towards hyperopia after cataract extraction with implantation of an IOL with insufficient refractive power [13,14,18].

The objective of the research is to study the clinical and ophthalmological features of children with congenital cataracts against the background of high myopia.

Material and methods. The study included 24 (40 eyes) children with cataracts and high myopia, who were undergoing inpatient treatment in the eye department of the clinic of Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute (TashPMI). The age of the children ranged from 1 year to 12 years. The average age of patients was 4.8 ± 1.2 years. All patients underwent ophthalmological (visometry, tonometry, biomicroscopy, ophthalmoscopy, tonometry, ultrasound scanning in A and B modes) examination methods. To assess the somatic status, patients were examined by a pediatrician,

neurologist, otolaryngologist, anesthesiologist and, if necessary, other specialists. Laboratory and instrumental examination methods were prescribed.

Results and discussion. Of the examined patients, there were 20 boys (83%) and 4 girls (17%). During the examination of patients by specialists, the following pathology was revealed: no pathology was revealed from the central nervous system in 4, from the musculoskeletal system in 2, and in from the internal organs in 18 patients.

Besides that, in the structure of concomitant pathology of the examined children, the most common was strabismus in 12 (50%) cases, convergent in 4 (17%), divergent in 6 (25%), vertical in 2 (8.3%) cases, respectively. Nystagmus was detected in 4 (16.6%) cases, in 2 (8.3%) cases, the patient had anterior microphthalmos. Visual acuity upon admission varied from 0.01 to 0.1 without correction.

During ultrabiomicroscopy (UBM) in older children, overstretching and local defects of the zonules were observed in 16 (40%) cases. Various variants of mesodermal dysgenesis of the anterior chamber were noted in 4 eyes (10%).

According to the nature of opacities during biomicroscopy, congenital cataracts were divided as follows: zonular cataracts were observed in 16 (40%) eyes, posterior capsular cataracts were observed in 14 (35%) eyes, and milky cataracts were observed in 10 (25%) eyes.

Additionally, during ophthalmoscopy (performed during or after surgery), hypoplasia of the optic disc was observed from the fundus in 6 (15%) eyes, and a myopic cone was observed in 14 (85%) eyes. Intraocular (IOP) pressure in all patients corresponded to the age norm.

What is more, during the A-scan ultrasound examination, the value of the anterior-posterior axis of the eye (APA) was higher than normal in all eyes, averaging 25.7 ± 2.1 mm. The thickness of the lens ranged from 2.13 mm to 4.93 mm.

According to the B-scan data, vitreous destruction of varying degrees of its manifestations was detected. According to the classification of Z.A. Makhacheva [4], destruction of degree I was diagnosed in 10 (25%), degree II - in 6 (15%), and degree III - in 4 (10%) eyes, respectively. Primary persistent vitreous (PHPV) was observed in 2 (5%) eyes. Complete posterior vitreous detachment (PVD) was detected in 12 (10%) cases, and incomplete PVD of varying height was determined in 22 (55%) cases, respectively. The issues concerning the age of the child at which it is advisable to implant an IOL into the eye cavity, the choice of its model and the calculation of the optical power remain debatable [5].

It is not a secret that all children under intubation anesthesia underwent aspiration and irrigation of cataract masses using Simkoec with primary implantation of spherical monoblock soft IOLs of the AlconIQ, AcrySof, Ocoflex models. The calculation of the refractive power of the IOL was performed using the SRKII formula with the expectation of obtaining a hypermetropic refraction taking into account the growth of the eye in accordance with the child's age. In 12 (30%) eyes, a posterior capsulorhexis was performed due to the presence of central posterior capsular opacities, and fibrosectomy was performed in 2 (5%) eyes. Intraoperatively, a defect in the posterior capsule of the lens, posterior lenticonus, was detected in 4 (10%) eyes. The diopter power of the intraocular lenses varied from +8.0 to +16.0 D. The results of keratometric parameters were in the range from 40.1 to 45.25 D. The following complications were observed intraoperatively in patients: rupture of the posterior lens capsule in 4 (10%) cases, vitreous leakage in 6 (15%), hyphema in 2 (5%) cases, respectively. Unplanned opening of the posterior lens capsule (10%)

occurred as a result of thinning of the posterior lens capsule, with lenticonus. After performing anterior vitrectomy, the intracapsular position of the IOL was achieved.

Undeniably, in the early postoperative period, the following complications were observed: corneal edema in 14 (35%) eyes, fibrin reaction was observed in 6 (15%) eyes. These children were prescribed frequent instillations of corticosteroid and nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, broad-spectrum antibiotics according to the scheme.

At discharge, visual acuity ranged from 0.08 to 0.4 (on average 0.15 ± 0.12). Low visual acuity in some patients was associated with the presence of hypoplasia of the optic disc. These children were prescribed trophic therapy 2 times a year.

Conclusion. By summarizing it should be suggested that in children with congenital cataract against the background of high myopia, zonular and posterior capsular forms of cataract are most often observed. The existing destruction, liquefaction and detachment of the vitreous body require minimally invasive surgical intervention using modern technologies in ophthalmic surgery.

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